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Ferroptosis in Cycling Hypoxia of Glioblastoma

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Abstract

JunD, a member of the activated protein-1 family of transcription factors, is a distinct protector for ischemia/reperfusion-induced injury in the liver or brain via its ability to reduce oxidative stress. However, the role of JunD in glioblastoma is obscure. In our proposal, we have demonstrated that cycling hypoxia, a specific type of tumour microenvironment (TME) differing from chronic hypoxia, was able to induce JunD activation in glioblastoma cells. Interestingly, knockdown of JunD in glioblastoma cells exhibited a decrease in cell viability under cycling hypoxia. Moreover, the treatments of ferroptosis inhibitors could restore these effects, suggesting JunD as a novel transcription factor involved in anti-ferroptosis under cycling hypoxia. Gene correlation analysis from clinical RNA-seq datasets in glioblastoma showed that GPX4 was most significantly associated with JunD compared to other anti-ferroptosis regulators. Bioinformatics analysis also identified two JunD binding sites in the human GPX4 promoter sequence from bases -2000 to +100. Based on these findings, we hypothesised that JunD promotes anti-ferroptosis by upregulating GPX4 under cycling hypoxia in glioblastoma. In this project, we have expanded on this hypothesis showing that knockdown of JUND decreased the expression of GPX4 *in vitro*. Furthermore, we have indicated that JUND is a conditional proto-oncogene that only exhibited its capability to maintain tumour proliferation *in vivo* but not *in vitro* normoxic TME. Combined with our proposal's preliminary findings, this project's results suggested that JunD is a conditional oncogenic transcription factor that sustains glioblastoma proliferation *in vivo* and guards cycling hypoxia-induced ferroptosis by activating GPX4.

Keywords: JunD, Glioblastoma, Tumour microenvironment, GPx4, Cycling hypoxia

Introduction

Glioblastoma Multiforme (GBM) represents one of the most fatal and refractory solid tumours in the adult central nervous system. Despite its relatively low incidence rate (3.23 per 100,000 population), glioblastoma is the most common malignant brain tumour and has an abysmal prognosis with a five-year survival rate of only 6.8% in the United States.¹ Ever since the seminal phase III trial in 2005 in which Stupp et al. consolidated the use of radiotherapy plus concomitant and adjuvant temozolomide (TMZ) after complete surgical resection,² no other therapeutic intervention has significantly altered this mainstay of confronting GBM.

Part of the reason behind this sluggish therapeutic advancement of GBM is its hostile intrinsic nature, which features genetic heterogeneity, infiltrative propensity, metabolic reprogramming, and renewable capability stemming from glioblastoma stem cells (GSCs).³ These intrinsic factors allow glioblastoma cells to evade immune responses and to survive therapeutic interventions while moving on to expand their territory by adapting to and reshaping the surrounding tumour microenvironment (TME). For instance, upon the threat of alkylating agents such as TMZ, around 60% of patients with unmethylated MGMT promoter (ranging from 53.4% to 67.9% depending on different clinical trials) dodge the attack from the TMZ-induced DNA double-stranded break by reversing this damage with functional MGMT instead of futile DNA mismatch repair.⁴ TMZ-resistant glioblastoma cells also enhance their cell division and anti-apoptosis ability by upregulating the signalling pathway of NRAS/MEK/ERK through the sponging effect between a circular RNA, CircASAP1, and a microRNA, MiR-502-5p. This RNA interaction frees up NRAS from being inhibited by MiR-502-5p.⁵ Apart from the above mentioned transcriptional and post-transcriptional modifications, post-translational mechanisms such as histone deacetylases (HDAC), specifically HDAC 1/2/6, enable glioblastoma cells to overcome TMZ-induced chemotoxicity by activating specificity protein 1 (sp1), which then evokes downstream pathways that promote anti-oxidative gene expression and tumour cell stemness.⁶ The intrinsic nature of TMZ-resistant GBM can further transmit lncRNA, fusion gene, and microRNA by exosome to alter the characteristics of nearby immune⁷, glia⁸, and glioblastoma cells⁹ toward a more tumorigenic state. In addition to TMZ-induced resistance, the inherent plasticity of glioblastoma cells covers the spectrum of therapy resistance induced by immunotherapy¹⁰ and to a lesser extent, radiotherapy¹¹, substantiating the current stalemate of the glioblastoma clinical trials.

On the other hand, the hostile extrinsic nature of GBM is mainly the aftermath of interplays between glioblastoma cells and their TME. Spatially, TME of GBM encompasses central necrotic zone, peripheral dysregulated vasculature, and intermediate hypoxic region, which together offers a dynamic place that sustains stresses and incubates glioblastoma progression.¹² Dispersing throughout this environment are cellular players, largely consisting of immune cells, astrocytes, neurons, and endothelial cells, which synergistically act as recipients of tumour influence as well as instigators of malignant transformation.¹³ Among these spatial features and cellular players, cycling hypoxia garners recent interest due to its unique characteristics of nurturing angiogenesis, therapy resistance, pro-tumoural inflammation, and metastasis.¹⁴ Cycling hypoxia originates when a solid tumour outgrowth its blood supplies, creating a central necrotic and chronic hypoxic zone while expanding into a perfusion-limited intermittent hypoxic region surrounded by poorly-growth vasculature.¹² In comparison with chronic hypoxia, cycling hypoxia possesses an additional temporal aspect in regards to its reoxygenation cycle. These inflows of blood after temporary hypoxic periods generate specific features, predominantly reactivation of ATP-driven mechanism¹⁵ and reactive oxygen species (ROS) production, aiding cells to reprogram signalling pathways in recovery from hypoxic shocks. Although chronic hypoxia also generates elevated ROS levels derived from mitochondrial complex III in the electron transport chain,¹⁶ cycling hypoxia levels up ROS with available oxygen molecules by activating oxidoreductases such as xanthine oxidase, NADPH oxidase (NOX), and cytochrome p450.¹⁷ This surge of ROS in cycling hypoxia initiates a more robust activation of HIF-1 α and NF- κ B, which upregulate genes expression related to pro-tumoural inflammation, angiogenesis, and attracting regulatory immunocytes.¹⁸ Moreover, in the context of GBM, the group of Hsieh et al. have reported that ROS-related regulatory mechanisms including NOX4, Bcl-x1, and ABCB1 can induce radioresistance¹⁹, chemoresistance^{20,21}, and tumour invasion plus infiltration²² under cycling hypoxia. Ultimately, excessive ROS generated by cycling hypoxic tumour cells confers worsened condition to GBM's TME and subsequent promotion of GBM progression.

Yet, how glioblastoma cells survive under this higher oxidative stress in cycling hypoxia requires further elucidation. Generally, cancer cells directly counter higher ROS levels by modifying their sulphur

metabolism, NADPH production, and activating the antioxidant defence system.²³ In other types of cancer cell lines, Rouschop et al. suggested that autophagy is required to lessen the ROS generated from cycling hypoxia,²⁴ which could result from the PERK-mediated cellular defence system.²⁵ A preprint from Sun et al. reveals an interesting finding that PI3K/AKT/HIF-1 α upregulates the expression of GPX4, a crucial anti-ferroptosis protein, under hypoxic condition and prevents ferroptosis in GBM.²⁶ Combining previous research showing upregulation of PI3K/AKT/HIF-1 α in endothelial cells under cycling hypoxia,²⁷ the HIF-1 α /GPX4 can well be an axis that lower cycling hypoxic ROS in GBM. Nevertheless, given its tumourigenic inclination and vast territory (spanning between 29 – 62% of tumour area in comparison to 23 to 54% of chronic hypoxia)¹⁸, cycling hypoxia is still a relevant target for countering the progression of GBM. Dissecting GBM's strategies of sustaining higher ROS in cycling hypoxia can illuminate future therapeutic approaches. Therefore, we proposed a novel hypothesis that JunD can defend ferroptosis in cycling hypoxic GBM by activating GPX4. Detailed literature review will be rigorously discussed in the next section.

Research aims

Specific aim 1: To observe the effect of tumour cycling hypoxia on the regulation of JunD.

Specific aim 2: To determine the role of JunD in cycling hypoxia-regulated ferroptosis.

Specific aim 3: To investigate the molecular mechanisms of JunD-regulated ferroptosis.

Literature review

JunD: a cell death modulator that potentially guards ferroptosis in cycling hypoxia

JunD is a JUN-related transcription factor that contains a basic leucine-zipper dimerization motif. JUN along with FOS, ATF, and MAF family are components of AP-1, a dimerized transcription factor that is tumourigenic or tumour-suppressive depending on its activating targets.²⁸ The main regulatory mechanisms of JunD is on the post-translational level, including cytoplasmic activation by mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs), such as extracellular signal-regulated kinases (ERKs) and c-JUN N-terminal kinases (JNKs), as well as nuclear inhibition by Multiple endocrine neoplasia type 1 (MEN1).²⁹ But dimerized JunD including JunD-FOS, JunD-MEN1, and JunD-JunD can also transcriptionally activate or repress the JunD gene expression through the binding on TPA response element (TRE) within the promoter region of JunD.²⁹ JunD is generally regarded as a cell protector by activating or repressing genes related to anti-apoptosis^{30,31} and anti-oxidative stress^{32,33}. However, the role of JunD in regulating ferroptosis under cycling hypoxia has not been intricately discussed, despite several research hinting at this possibility. Cycling hypoxia may regulate JunD function via post-translational and transcriptional mechanisms. Although both chronic hypoxia³⁴ and cycling hypoxia²² upregulate the activity of ERKs and JNKs, chronic hypoxia lessens the amount of phosphorylated JunD in lung tissues,³⁴ while the effect of cycling hypoxia on the JunD's activity remains unexplored. In comparison, the gene expression of JunD in peripheral red blood cells trends downward in an ischaemia-reperfusion stroke model.³⁵ However, given the importance of JunD on maintaining cell survival in ischaemia-reperfusion cells,³⁵ it is very possible that in spite of the transcriptional inhibition possibly driven by the negative feedback loop of JunD-FOS heterodimer,³⁶ the activity of JunD rather goes up through the increased function of JNKs and ERKs in glioblastoma cells.²² Regarding the links between JunD and ferroptosis, Gerald et al. have observed an accumulation of Fe³⁺ in JunD^{-/-} fibroblast, which infers the consequences of ferroptosis by overproduction of PLOOH and resulting Fenton reaction.³² Additionally, in a hepatocarcinoma model, JunD may activate ferritin heavy chain (ferritin H), an iron storage protein counteracting ferroptosis in cardiomyopathy,³⁷ by binding to its antioxidant response element.³⁸ In contrast, JunD can induce lipid accumulation in pancreatic β cells by upregulating genes associated with lipid metabolism,³⁹ which may induce ferroptosis by enriching PUFAs.⁴⁰ Overall, JunD can suppress or promote ferroptosis according to different cellular contexts. In the preliminary data presented in the proposal of this report, we've revealed that cycling hypoxia can increase nuclear JunD expression, and reduces the cell viability of JUND knockdown cells, which could be rescued by ferroptosis inhibitors. These results has pointed out the potential role of JunD in countering ferroptosis in GBM under cycling hypoxia.

GPX4: a nexus between ferroptosis and cycling hypoxia

Glutathione peroxidase 4 (GPX4) is a crucial detoxifying enzyme that catalyses the reduction of phospholipid hydroperoxides (PLOOHs), which are a member of the ROS family and the main contributors to ferroptosis, a programmed cell death driven by iron-dependent phospholipid peroxidation.⁴¹ Recent research has reported several links between hypoxia and ferroptosis in cancer. Hypoxia can promote or counter ferroptosis by altering signalling pathways related to lipid and iron metabolism. On the promoting side, cancer cells that constitutively express a high level of HIFs can be prone to ferroptosis. For instance, intrinsic expression of HIF-2 α in clear cell renal cell carcinoma can enrich polyunsaturated fatty acids, a component for lipid peroxidation, and thus increase its vulnerability to ferroptosis by upregulating hypoxia-induced, lipid droplet-associated protein.⁴² By a similar pathway, a high level of HIF-2 α in colorectal cancer can drive the expression of iron and lipid regulatory genes, casting ferroptotic susceptibility to this type of cancer.⁴³ On the other hand, hypoxic cancer cells can also resist pressure from ferroptosis by upregulating protective enzymes and transcription factors. Under hypoxic treatment, mesothelioma enhances its gene expression of carbonic anhydrase IX to prevent dysregulated iron metabolism (upregulation of TFRC, IREB1/2, FPN1; downregulation of FTH/FTL) and subsequent ferroptotic and apoptotic death.⁴⁴ Considering cycling hypoxia, nuclear factor erythroid 2-related factor (NRF2) has been implicated more commonly in ischaemia-reperfusion injury but also under cycling hypoxia in adenocarcinoma.⁴⁵ The transactivating targets for NRF2 are involved in preventing ferroptosis: including iron metabolism (ABCB6, BLVRA/B, FECH etc.), intermediate metabolism (AKR1B1, AKR1B10, G6PD etc.), and Glutathione synthesis (SLC7A11, GSTA, GSS etc.).⁴⁶ Nonetheless, how cycling hypoxia regulates ferroptosis through PLOOHs detoxifying system, the three major players being GPX4, ferroptosis suppressor protein 1 (FSP1)^{47,48}, and dihydroorotate dehydrogenase (DHODH)⁴⁹, requires additional clarifications. In the proposal, we have conducted gene expression correlation analyses in RNA-seq datasets and promoter region analyses to indicate that JUND could be involved in the activation of GPX4. Therefore JunD may also warrant as another guarding factor of ferroptosis via initiating GPX4 expression under cycling hypoxia in GBM.

Methods

Cell culture

Murine GL261 glioma cells were kindly provided by Dr. Chi-Shiun Chiang (Department of Biomedical Engineering and Environmental Sciences, National Tsing Hua University, Taiwan). Human glioblastoma cell line GBM8401 was obtained from Bioresource Collection and Research Center (BCRC). GL261 cells were cultured in DMEM (Life Technologies) supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS), 10 mM HEPES, and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. GBM8401 cells were maintained in RPMI 1640 (Invitrogen) with 10% FBS, 10 mM HEPES, and 1% penicillin-streptomycin. All cells were incubated under 37°C supplemented with 5% CO₂.

Vector construction and viral transduction

The pGreenFire1-SFFV²² was used to generate glioma reporter cells (GL261-lucGFP) bearing SFFV promoter-driven dual optical reporter genes encoding both green fluorescence protein (GFP) and luciferase (Luc). Lentiviral vectors carrying short hairpin RNA (shRNA)-targeting *Homo sapiens* JUND: JUND_974H (5'-GCGCCTGGAAGAGAAAGTGAA-3'), JUND_975H (5'-TGGAGGATTTACACAAGCAGA-3'), *Mus musculus* Jund: JUND_093M (5'-GTTCGCCGAAGGCTTCGTCAA-3'), JUND_704M (5'-GAGAAAGTCAAGACCTCAAA-3'), and scrambled shRNA (vector backbone) (https://rna.genmed.sinica.edu.tw/file/vector/Others/02.pLKO.1-puro_Map.pdf) were provided by the National RNAi core facility, Academia Sinica in Taiwan. Lentivirus production begins by co-transfecting 293T cells with the designated lentiviral vectors, the packaging plasmid pCMV Δ R8.91, and the envelope plasmid pMD.G by jetPRIME[®] (Polyplus-transfection[®] SA) transfection reagent. At 24 and 48 h after transfection, the viral particles in the culture medium were harvested and stored at -80°C until use. GL261-lucGFP and GBM8401 cells were infected with designated lentivirus in the presence of Polybrene (Sigma) at a final concentration of 8 μ g/mL for 24 h and subject to puromycin selection (1 μ g/mL for 48 h; 2 μ g/mL for 48 h; 2.5 μ g/mL for 24 h). JUND knockdown performance in each type of cell was measured by qPCR.

Real-time quantitative polymerase chain reaction (qPCR)

RNAs in each type of cells were extracted using NucleoZol (MACHEREY-NAGEL) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The extracted RNAs were reversed-transcribed into cDNAs by iScript™ Reverse Transcription Supermix for RT-qPCR (Bio-Rad) according to the manufacturer's protocol (PCR thermal sequences: 25°C for 5 min, 46°C for 20 min, 95°C for 1 min, 4°C for final maintenance) (T100™ Thermal Cycler, Bio-Rad). The resulting cDNAs were diluted to the same concentration measured by a spectrophotometer (MN-913A, MaestroGen). Then, the cDNAs (1 µL) were mixed with primers of target genes (1 µL for each forward and reverse primers), 2× SYBR® Green Master Mix (Bio-Rad; 10 µL), and RNase-free water (7 µL). Finally, the mixture underwent qPCR thermal cycles to amplify quantitatively (95°C for 10 min, 95°C for 15 sec, 58°C for 30 sec, plate read plus loop back to 95°C for 15 sec for 39 times, 95°C for 10 sec, 65°C for 5 min, 72°C to 95°C at 0.5°C/sec (plate read)) (CFX96™ Touch Real-Time PCR System, Bio-Rad). The primers used in this study were: *Jund* (*Mus musculus*) (Forward) 5'-ACACGCAAGAACGCATCAAG-3' (Reverse) 5'-AGCTCGGTGTTCTGGCTTTT-3'; *JUND* (*Homo sapiens*) (Forward) 5'-CCCTTTCCTCGATCTCGCTC-3' (Reverse) 5'-CGGGCGAACCAAGGATTACA-3'; *GAPDH* (*Homo sapiens*) (Forward) 5'-GCACAAGAGGAAGAGAGACC-3' (Reverse) 5'-AGGGGAGATTCAGTGTGGTG-3'; *Gapdh* (*Mus musculus*) (Forward) 5'-AAATGGTGAAGGTCGGTGTG-3' (Reverse) 5'-GAATTTGCCGTGAGTGGAGT-3'.

Cell proliferation assay

The trypan blue dye exclusion test was used to determine the number of cells: GL261-lucGFP infected with *JUND* shRNAs or vector plasmid were seeded in 24-well plates (1×10^4 cells/well), harvested on designated days by trypsin/EDTA, and enumerated with a Neubauer hemocytometer after trypan blue staining (trypan blue : cell suspension = 1 : 1).

Animal model

Six-week-old male C57BL/6J mice were purchased from the Animal Facility of the National Science Council. C57BL/6J mice were utilised to create a syngeneic orthotopic glioblastoma mouse model according to a published method.⁵⁰ 3×10^5 GL261-lucGFP cells infected with *JUND* shRNAs or vector plasmid were implanted into the right basal ganglia of anaesthetised mice. The tumours were developed 18 days after implantation, extracted and submerged in 4% PFA for 1 d, immersed in 30% sucrose for 7 d, frozen-embedded in OCT with liquid nitrogen, and stored under -80°C .

Bioluminescent imaging

Mice bearing GL261-lucGFP infected with *JUND* shRNAs or vector plasmid were imaged by the IVIS Imaging System 200 Series (PerkinElmer) to monitor the bioluminescence from the inoculated tumours. Mice were first anaesthetised with isoflurane (2.5%) in the imaging chamber and intraperitoneally injected with D-luciferin (250 µg/g body weight; PerkinElmer). BLI was captured 15 min after D-luciferin injection. For quantitative analyses of the BLI signal, signaling intensities in the acquired intraperitoneal region were defined as the total number of photons (sec-1; steradian-1; centimeter-2) with Living Image Software (ver. 2.60.1).

Bioinformatic data analysis

JunD gene expression among oligodendrocyte progenitor cells, neoplastic cells, vascular cells, myeloid cells, neurons, oligodendrocytes, and astrocytes in a human scRNA-seq glioblastoma dataset are graphed with the online module provided by the authors.⁵¹

Statistical analysis

Cell proliferation numbers are presented as the mean \pm SD. Fold difference in qPCR analysis is presented as mean (upper and lower limit). Unpaired two-tailed t-tests were performed with GraphPad Prism 9.5.1.

Results

JunD is a conditional proto-oncogene regulated by the glioblastoma tumour microenvironment.

Previously in our proposal, we've validated that cycling hypoxia may enhance the nuclear expression of JunD and diminish cell viability in JUND-knockdown cells, suggesting JunD's capability in promoting tumour cell viability. In this report, we elaborated this concept by demonstrating that JunD is a conditional proto-oncogene that only exerts its tumour-protecting effects under *in vivo* tumour microenvironment (TME) but not under *in vitro* normoxic culturing. *In vitro* cell proliferation status between GL261-lucGFP infected with vector plasmid and those infected with JUND shRNAs were closely adhered with each other. In addition, the final proliferation numbers of the JUND-knockdown group were not significantly different from that of the vector group. This suggests that under normoxic cell culturing (5% CO₂, 37°C), JunD does not influence glioblastoma's proliferation status. However, upon implanting JUND-knockdown and vector-infected GL261-lucGFP into the basal ganglia of syngeneic C57BL/6J, the sizes of tumour spheres measured by bioluminescent imaging in vector-infected GL261-lucGFP were substantially larger than those of JUND-knockdown GL261-lucGFP at 7th day of tumour implantation. This revealed that certain elements distinguishing *in vitro* and *in vivo* settings, possibly a hypoxic environment, activate or enhance JUND's capability to support tumour growth.

JunD activates GPx4 gene expression in glioblastoma *in vitro*

Our preliminary studies have proven that JunD is protective against ferroptosis in glioblastoma cells under cycling hypoxia and hypothesised that activation of GPx4 gene transcription by JunD binding to its promoter region could be the underlying mechanism. Here we utilised qPCR analysis to prove that JunD activates GPx4 at the gene transcription level since the gene expression of GPx4 decreased when JUND had been knocked down in human glioblastoma cells. This concurred with our hypothesis on JunD's role in guarding against ferroptosis in glioblastoma via upregulating GPx4, a significant ferroptosis protector.

Figure 1. JUND is a conditional proto-oncogene regulated by the glioblastoma tumour microenvironment. (A) Cell proliferation of GL261-lucGFP infected with vector plasmid (pLKO.1) and JUND shRNA (JUND_093M, JUND_704M) *in vitro*. Unpaired two-tailed t-tests were performed for the cell numbers at 120 h. ns represents P value > 0.05. (B) Bioluminescent imaging of GL261-lucGFP orthografts infected with vector plasmid (pLKO.1) and JUND shRNA (JUND_093M, JUND_704M) at day 7 after tumour implantation. Unit: radiance (p/sec/cm²/sr); color scale: min = 1.5 × 10⁵, max = 2.3 × 10⁶. JUND knockdown performance of GL261-lucGFP is presented in Table 1.

Figure 2. JunD activates GPx4 gene expression in glioblastoma *in vitro*. qPCR expression fold change in GPX4 relative to vector in GBM8401 infected with vector plasmid (pLKO.1) and JUND shRNA (JUND_974H, JUND_975H). Unpaired two-tailed t-tests were performed for the \log_2FC . * $0.01 < P$ value < 0.05 ; ** $0.001 < P$ value < 0.01 . JUND knockdown performance of GBM8401 is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. JUND knockdown performance in GL261-lucGFP infected with JUND shRNA

Sample	JUND Mean C_T	GAPDH Mean C_T	ΔC_T	$\Delta\Delta C_T$	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$
Vector	21.45±0.04	15.34±0.01	6.10±0.04	0±0.04	1 (0.98-1.03)
JUND_093M	21.96±0.03	14.94±0.13	7.02±0.14	0.92±0.14	0.53 (0.48-0.58)
JUND_704M	22.17±0.00	15.21±0.03	6.97±0.03	0.86±0.03	0.55 (0.54-0.56)

Notes — $\Delta\Delta C_T$: ΔC_T kd – ΔC_T vector; ΔC_T : JUND-GAPDH; $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$: Fold difference in JUND relative to vector

Table 2. JUND knockdown performance in GBM8401 infected with JUND shRNA

Sample	JUND Mean C_T	GAPDH Mean C_T	ΔC_T	$\Delta\Delta C_T$	$2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$
Vector	17.95±0.21	16.42±0.02	1.53±0.21	0±0.21	1 (0.86-1.16)
JUND_974H	18.43±0.07	16.12±0.14	2.31±0.16	0.78±0.16	0.58 (0.52-0.65)
JUND_975H	18.50±0.04	16.26±0.01	2.24±0.04	0.71±0.04	0.61 (0.59-0.63)

Notes — $\Delta\Delta C_T$: ΔC_T kd – ΔC_T vector; ΔC_T : JUND-GAPDH; $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_T}$: Fold difference in JUND relative to vector

Discussion

Glioblastoma tumour microenvironment (TME) encompasses multiple aspects, including immune cells infiltration and activation, oligodendrocytes precursor cells (OPCs)-induced stemness, angiogenesis of tumour-associated vasculature, and hypoxic redox stresses. In this project, we hinted at the possible involvement of TME in nurturing JunD's promotion of tumour proliferation by discovering that *in vivo* growth of JUND-knockdown GL261-lucGFP is substantially slower than the control group. Therefore, determining which aspects of *in vivo* TME are warranted for JunD's conditional proto-oncogenic phenomena is worth exploring.

Indeed, we will conduct IHC studies to test whether ferroptosis exist in JUND-knockdown glioblastoma and whether cycling hypoxia overlays in these ferroptotic region. This could validate our hypothesis that glioblastoma counters the excess redox stresses in cycling hypoxic areas by activating JUND/GPX4 and alleviating ferroptosis *in vivo*. To consolidate the activation of GPX4 by JunD, we will induce point mutation or deletion in the predicted binding sites of JunD in GPX4 promoter-driven luciferase reporter gene and observe bioluminescent intensity after the knockdown of JUND. ChIP assay will also be performed to validate the binding of JunD in the GPX4 promoter region.

Additionally, certain elements downstream of JunD signal transduction may prevail upon activation by *in vivo* TME, including suppressing tumour neoantigen that helps glioblastoma evade immune surveillance. Nevertheless, this conjecture requires further exploration in glioblastoma RNA-seq datasets since previous studies only validated JunD's roles on T-cell activation⁵² and IL-7 regulating signalling pathway⁵³, not on JunD's capability to suppress tumour neoantigen. Therefore gene expression analysis of the JunD downstream target in glioblastoma should be conducted and evaluated before proceeding to cell and animal experiments.

Apart from immune-related responses, OPCs have been proven to be a crucial cell component in regenerating glioblastoma after complete tumour resection and temozolomide therapy.⁵⁴ Interestingly, preliminary data explorations using a scRNA-seq glioblastoma dataset⁵¹, including cell types like OPCs, neoplastic cells, vascular cells, myeloid cells, neurons, oligodendrocytes, and astrocytes, revealed that OPCs have the highest expression of JunD among other cell types; furthermore, peripheral OPCs express higher JUND compared to the tumour core counterpart (Supplementary Figure A, B). This revelation suggested that JunD may be a significant transcription factor for OPCs to promote malignant progression on the tumour periphery. Notwithstanding, does the expression of JunD within glioblastoma alter the *in vivo* expression of JunD in OPCs by tumour-related secretome, ultimately leading to tumour progression or regeneration? By way of alternatives, could some GL261-lucGFP exhibit OPCs-like characteristics upon interacting with *in vivo* TME, and that JunD plays a crucial role in these cells to sustain tumour proliferation? Regardless of each scenario, we will explore the first hypothesis by co-culturing other glioblastoma cells or OPCs with the medium used to culture JUND knockdown cells, observing tumour proliferation speed, and measuring JunD gene and protein expression in the co-cultured cells. Moreover, we will test the second hypothesis by utilising IHC to co-stain OPCs markers and JunD in JUND-knockdown and control glioblastoma. This will determine whether JunD is correlated with the presence of OPCs or OPCs-like GL261-lucGFP.

In conclusion, we elaborated on our preliminary findings that cycling hypoxia can activate JunD expression to counter ferroptosis by showing that GPx4 was reduced on the gene transcription level upon JUND knockdown. We also demonstrated that JunD is a conditional proto-oncogene that only exerts its tumour-protective effect within *in vivo* TME. However, which aspects of *in vivo* TME — cycling hypoxia-induced ferroptosis, neoantigen-related immune response, or malignant transformation mediated by OPCs — are responsible for JUND's conditional proto-oncogene require further exploration in both *in vitro* and *in vivo* experiments.

Obstacles encountered in this project

During the execution of this project, we experienced difficulties establishing stable gene knockdown in both human (GBM8401) and mouse (GL261-lucGFP) high-grade glioma cells. The JUND-knockdown cells were either prone to death or underwent rebound JunD gene expression after subsequent subculturing. These issues were eventually resolved by gradually increasing the antibiotics selection concentration after shRNA infection, followed by a brief spike of selection concentration over the pretested lethal dosage for each cell type to ensure complete eradication of antibiotic-resistant parental cells (The detailed protocol is presented in the method section).

Supplementary Figure: JUND is highly expressed within oligodendrocyte progenitor cells (OPCs) in the glioblastoma tumour microenvironment. (A) JunD gene expression among OPCs, neoplastic cells, vascular cells, myeloid cells, neurons, oligodendrocytes, and astrocytes in glioblastoma TME. **(B)** JunD gene expression in OPCs around glioblastoma core or periphery. scRNA-seq gene expression explorations were conducted through processed data provided online.⁵¹

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